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TECHNOLOGY DISRUPTION AND BUSINESS PERFORMANCE IN SMEs

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Abstract - With the advent of industrial 4.0, more and more enterprises and business entities are moving towards technology and digital based platform. Contextualising the topic to Malaysian scenario, the country is in the verge of adoption of this industrial change very fast in comparison with other South East Asian countries. A quantitative cross sectional study was conducted to analyse the impact of Technology Disruption, Competence Depletion on and Business Performance. The study follows purposive sampling among the employees at the small and micro enterprises of Selangor state of Malaysia. The study used PLS SEM to estimate the model. The research has pointed out practical and managerial implications to the management of micro and small scale industries.

Keywords: Technology disruption, Competence Depletion, Business Performance, Innovation Capability

I. INTRODUCTION

Though several studies have conducted in the large scale industrial organisations, seldom such effort observed in the micro and small enterprises exploring the relationship between professional obsolescence and its impact on innovation capability and business performance. It is pointed out that as manufacturing work continues to shift from manual labour to the programming and control of high-performance machines [1], the skills deficit of the workforce may increase as develops. The professional competence will be one among the several factors modern SMEs need to be looked into for productivity and business performance in the industry 4.0 era. Through this study, the researcher endeavors to throw light on the impact of professional obsolescence which is relevant in the wake of industry 4.0, where majority functional domain has taken over by the technology interventions away from human interventions.

II. LITERATURE AND HYPOTHESIS

Technology disruption and business performance

Wang [2] explained the need of improving organization's Innovation capacity in order to adapt to the advanced technological systems so as to move

faster than the competition. Such competitive pressure among the firms are increasing globally, resulting into reduced life cycle of technologies and products, and putting companies to compelling proposition of innovation. Changes in the technology have forced the market to look into modern ways of production and distribution for better business performance. Research on technology disruption impact on the business performance is less researched into on the micro and small industries in the wake of industry 4.0. Hence this study proposes the following hypothesis as;

H1. There will be significant relationship between technology disruption and business performance in micro and small business enterprises.

Employee Competence and business performance

The requirement of developing newer and futuristic competencies as the need of the hour to maintain the OH has been highlighted by many a researcher in the recent past [3] [4]. March [5] further elaborated saying firms which seek and explore new opportunities by upgrading the competence will sustain in the market and improve performance. To be able to implement the business strategy successfully, the firm needs to address the most important question of its workforce competence needs for the future [6]. Seldom any research was conducted to establish the relationship between human employee competence and business performance in the micro and small industries in the wake of industry 4.0. Hence this study proposes the following hypothesis as;

H2. There will be significant relationship between employee competence and business performance in micro and small business enterprises.

Innovation Capability and business performance

As it is indicated by Robert [7], there is a need of improving the innovation capacity of the organisations in order to adapt to the advanced technological systems so as to move faster than the competition. As it is evidenced the pressure between the firms are increasing globally, that necessitate changes in the life cycle of technologies and products and services, and forcing companies into engaging innovation [8]. In the

wake of industry 4.0 very less attempt have been made by the past researchers to explore the relationship between Innovation Capability and business performance in the micro and small industries. Hence this study proposes the following hypothesis as;

H3. There will be significant relationship between employee competence and business performance in micro and small business enterprises.

Technology Disruption, Employee Competence and business performance

Contextual imbalances created by the technology disruption can be neutralized to a great extent through competence intervention and thus effort should be directed towards creating and sustaining perfect levels of [9], [10],[11]. Indeed, in managing innovation, the major role of management is to create an environment in the firm to innovate which can improve the firm’s capacity of innovation [26]. Seldom was any research conducted to establish the relationship between human technology disruption and business performance with moderating effect of employee competence in the micro and small industries in the wake of industry 4.0. Hence this study proposes the following hypothesis as;

H4. There will be significant relationship between employee competence and business performance in micro and small business enterprises.

Technology disruption, Innovation capacity and business performance

Empirical evidences of the correlation between innovation capacity and organizational performance in terms of market share and profitability have been confirmed by the researchers in many a study in the past [12]. Organisations which are focused and committed towards fulfilling the real-time demands of the industry on technology will have better chance of growth in comparison to their competitors. While are fewer studies conducted in the wake of industrial 4.0 to establish the relationship between Technology disruption, Innovation capacity and business performance with mediation effects of Innovation capacity in the micro and small industries. Hence this study proposes the following hypothesis as;

H5. There will be significant relationship between employee competence and business performance in micro and small business enterprises.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Sampling

The sample for this research focused on working workers. Those who have at least 5 years’ experience in the organisation was considered for the study. The objective of such selection is to ensure that the

respondents can provide adequate information on the impact of technology change in the SMEs, where they are working with. The researcher collected 384 questionnaires back from 425 set of questionnaire distributed, and the study followed purposive sampling. The study location is the Klang Valley region of Malaysia, where maximum number of micro and small industries are located in the Selangor state of Malaysia.

TABLE 1 MEASUREMENT

No	Variables	No. of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha	Author
1	Technology disruption	16	0.84	Ryan and Harrison (2001) (dimensions from Kaufman (1974)
2	Employee competence	16	0.79	Mohan & Chauhan, 2000
3	Innovation Capacity	7	0.75	Jansen, J., Van den Bosch, F., and Volberda, H. (2006)
4	Business performance	6	0.85	Li, W., Valiyath, R., & Tan, J. (2013).

Based on the questionnaire adopted the table shows that the Cronbach’s Alpha for the technology disruption is 0.84 and Employee competence is 0.79. While the Cronbach’s Alpha for employee competence is .74 and almost similar goes with Innovation Capacity is 0.85. Overall scores shows that the Cronbach’s Alpha exceeding 0.7 [18]. Hence, it can be assumed that internal consistency for this questionnaire is considered to be good.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Figure 1. Theoretical Framework overall effect

TABLE 2 OVERVIEW OF DIRECT RELATION

Hypothetical Relationship (Direct Effect)	Path Coefficient t	Absolute t statistic value	Value of R ²	Value of Q ²
TD→BP	0.501***	17.123	0.699	0.609
EC→BP	0.580***	18.201	0.702	0.659
IC→BP	0.600***	19.821	0.721	0.699
TD→EC→BP	0.609***	19.010	0.710	0.688
TD→IC→BP	0.599***	18.010	0.709	0.649

Hair [21] posited that there are four key criteria for assessing the structural model in PLSSEM. These include assessments of: (1) significance of the path coefficients, (2) coefficient determination (R^2), (3) the effect size (f^2), and lastly (4) predictive relevance (Q^2). This particular study has posed five hypotheses which consist of the three direct and two indirect analyses. Chin [19] classified the R-squared of .19, .33 and .67 as weak, moderate and substantial respectively.

The composite model which has come out the overall analysis indicates that the entire hypothesis considered for the study is well established the causation with the overall predictability of 69.9% with high beta coefficients. Thus, the R^2 in this study can be classified as substantial. In particular, a cross-validated redundancy measure (Q^2) was applied to assess the predictive relevance of the research model [19],[20],[21],[22],[23]. According to Henseler and Fassott [24], a research model with Q^2 statistic (s) greater than zero is considered to have predictive relevance. Additionally, a research model with higher positive Q^2 values suggests more predictive relevance. The table 2 shows the predictive relevance of the model produced in this research.

V. DISCUSSION

The overall study establishes the strong relationship between technological disruption and business performance in small and medium scale industries. Based on the findings small and medium scale sector industries have to invest more in technology in order to succeed under increasingly challenging conditions. The technological disruption invites several changes in order to respond to the uncertain and unexpected changes in the market to sustain the business like, prompt decision-making, internal flexibility, more willingness to take risks, more entrepreneurial spirit etc. to remain competitive in business. Disruptive innovation provides a dominant possibility for growth through new market discovery for SMEs.

Disruption has become the standard for several small and medium scale industries. During the disruptive change major factor get influenced is the employee competence. The disruption of technology also invites HR disruption. The invasion of technological disruptions, where SME's can grow beyond HR

compliance and emphasis on driving people improvement and competencies for business development. It is imperative that the HR should ensure updated job related skills and abilities which is in tune with the technological advancement resources for future business requirements. The study results indicate strong relationship between employee competence and technology disruption. A better employee competence necessitated by the technology disruption will be leading better business performance. This requires firms to develop and maintain a complex competence management process to sustain the competitive advantage.

Equally envisaged is the importance of innovation capacity of the small and medium scale industries to One of the major factor which regulate the technology disruption is organizations capacity to absorb the technology changes. Innovation is no more an option for companies, as the competitive spirit in the market place is increasing with the global consumer pressure [25]. SMEs which desire to sustain business performance should ensure continuous improvement in collective innovation capacity. The SMEs should be able to update and improve the current resource capacities that absorb the changes effectively for better business performance. SMEs should do be able to develop novel, affordable products/services by taking advantages of this disruptive innovation and innovation capacity which facilitate better business growth.

The study posed two hypotheses to analyze the moderation effect. It is clear from the findings that employee competence and innovation capacity fully moderate the relationship between technology disruption and business performance. This indicates that the pace of technological disruption is fully regulated by a competence work force as well as innovation capacity of the organization. If the HR manager won't be able to focus on the employee competence during technological disruption SMEs cannot reap the benefits of technology changes. Similar scenario goes with innovation capacity also. Ensuring better adoption of innovation capabilities by the organization can change the outcome of business performance.

VI. IMPLICATIONS

A. Practical implications

When newer generations of technology emerge over a short span of period, leaving the previous versions rapidly obsolete, the skills which were then required to manage the versions also become obsolete. Competence depletion is a serious concern for technology companies as they grapple with the ever

changing competence requirements to keep up with the technology demands. Technology disruption not only depletes accumulated competence required for the current line, but also offers competitive opportunities to appropriate competence. However, several organizations often lack sufficient competence adequacy to take on sudden and unexpected changes. The findings of the current research better establish the impact of technology disruption on business performance. The research throws better understanding on the serious situation of technology disruption and the resultant business performance problems the SMEs may face during industry 4.0 and it support better competence preparedness for technology changes for the SMEs in Malaysia.

B. Theoretical implications

The research contributes to the competence theory by integrating the moderating factors of Innovation Capacity and employee competence. The study tried to build up the level of competence required for maintaining business performance in a changing technological environment, thus putting forward a resource-innovation-competence equilibrium model. Competitive advantages can almost always be explained by human resources. Thus, following the resource based view theory integration of HRM practices with technology integration, innovation capacity and strategic management is essential in order to develop and sustain competitive advantages

VII. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to establish the relationship between technology disruption and business performance in the wake of industry 4.0, with the intervening effects of employee competence and innovation capacity. The study clearly establish the strong relationship between the independent and dependent variables explaining the impact of technology disruption on Business development in small and medium scale industries in Malaysia. The study paves better practical implications to the HR managers of SMEs in their prominent role in workforce competence building. It also envisages the need of top management commitment in ensuring a work culture which facilitates innovation capacities by proper resource management when SMEs faces the effect of technology disruption.

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